

HEALTH BELIEF MODEL AND KNOWLEDGE GAP THEORY APPLIED TO COVID-19

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Table of Contents

Abstract	4
Thesis Statement	5
The COVID-19 Pandemic.....	5
SARS-CoV-2 Virus	5
COVID-19 Policies.....	7
Policymakers Involved.....	8
Messages Communicated by the Policymakers	11
Messages from Policymakers to Stakeholders.....	13
Stakeholders Involved.....	14
Messages Communicated by Stakeholders	15
Constituents.....	17
Messages Among the Constituents	17
Messages from Constituents to Stakeholders and Policymakers	18
Civic Engagement and the Consideration of the Position of Constituents	19
Policy Outcome.....	20
COVID-19 Pandemic and Compliance.....	22
Compliance and Political Affiliation	23
Compliance and Gender Differences	23
Trust in the Government	24
Compliance and Social Norms.....	25
Application of Theories to COVID-19 Regulation and Policy Adoption.....	26
Health Belief Model.....	26
Health Belief Model and S-R Theorists.....	26
Components of Health Belief Model and Application to the COVID-19 Pandemic.....	28
Perceived susceptibility	29
Perceived Severity	29
Perceived Benefits	30
Perceived Barriers.....	30
Cues to Action.....	31
Self-Efficacy	31
HBM: Influence and Efficacy of Communications During the COVID-19 Pandemic	32
Policymaker and Stakeholder Communication with HBM	34
Knowledge Gap Theory	36
Components of Knowledge Gap Theory and Application to the COVID-19 Pandemic	37
Communication Skills.....	37
Relevant Social Contact.....	38
The Extent of Prior Knowledge	38

Selective Exposure, Acceptance, and Retention of Information	39
Nature of Mass Media Information Delivery Systems	40
Knowledge Gap Theory: Influence and Efficacy of Communications During COVID-19	40
The Term Social Distancing	42
Policymaker and Stakeholder Communication with Knowledge Gap Theory	42
Success or Failure of the Communications	43
Conclusion	45
References	49
Appendices	59
Appendix A – Donald Trump Response to COVID-19	59
Appendix B – Mayo Clinic Response to COVID-19	60
Appendix C – Mayo Clinic Response to COVID-19	61
Appendix D – Mayo Clinic Fact Check	62
Appendix E – Heartland Dental Response to COVID-19	63
Appendix F – Heartland Dental Response to COVID-19	64
Appendix G – Walmart Response to COVID-19	65
Appendix H – Constituent Responses to Walmart	66
Appendix I – Constituent Responses to Mayo Clinic	67
Appendix J – Constituent Responses to Donald Trump	68

Abstract

This paper covers the COVID-19 pandemic and explains how regulations and policies were communicated to the public. The first section dives into the case history of the COVID-19 pandemic and the policies, procedures, and regulations that followed. It explains who the policymakers, stakeholders, and constituents were and what type of messages they communicated throughout the crisis. Even though preventative measures were communicated to the public and attempted, there were still millions of deaths from the COVID-19 pandemic. Research was conducted to suggest that measures such as stay-at-home orders, restrictions on large gatherings, closures of educational facilities, and non-essential businesses could have effectively reduced transmission rates and "flattened the curve," with stay-at-home orders having had the most significant impact. Several factors contributed to an individual's compliance with governmental COVID-19 policies during the pandemic, including social norms, trust in the government, gender differences, and, most apparent, political affiliation. The paper's second half describes and applies two communication theories, the Health Belief Model and the Knowledge Gap Theory, to the COVID-19 pandemic. The Health Belief Model can explain how perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefits, perceived barriers, cues to action, and self-efficacy contributed to whether individuals adopted COVID-19 regulations. The Health Belief Model, when applied to the COVID-19 pandemic, can explain the benefits and barriers people perceive when they decide to change their health behavior and how those contribute to their decision-making process.

Additionally, it explains that people are at different stages of their perceived severity and susceptibility to contracting the virus and getting sick from COVID-19. Knowledge Gap Theory explains that low socioeconomic groups did not have the same access to COVID-19 information

as high socioeconomic groups. The paper will use the Knowledge Gap Theory to explain how lower socioeconomic groups may not have understood information about COVID-19 regulations and policies as fast and consistent as higher socioeconomic groups. It will then explain what types of components kept the perpetuating knowledge gaps during the COVID-19 pandemic to continue. This paper also describes the efficacy of communication during the COVID-19 pandemic by applying the Health Belief Model and Knowledge Gap Theory to the case history.

Thesis Statement

The Health Belief Model and the Knowledge Gap Theory can explain why some populations did not adopt COVID-19 policies, regulations, and behavior changes. The Health Belief Model explains that there are key perceived reasons why some people did and did not adopt COVID-19 regulations that could help keep them disease-free. The Knowledge Gap Theory further suggests that people in lower socioeconomic populations had less access to information about COVID-19 and thus were more likely not to adopt COVID-19 policy as quickly.

The COVID-19 Pandemic

SARS-CoV-2 Virus

In December 2019, a new coronavirus emerged in Asia, leading to potentially severe pneumonia (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). This virus, SARS-CoV-2, led to COVID-19, an infectious disease (World Health Organization: WHO, 2020). The virus became the cause of the worldwide COVID-19 pandemic and global health crisis. This global health crisis has extensively affected different aspects of society, including individual well-being, social interactions, cultural norms, public health systems, and economic stability (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). SARS-CoV-2 is mainly spread through respiratory secretions during close and extended contact, presenting a substantial

risk when an infected person coughs, sneezes, or talks, potentially leading to inhalation or contact with mucous membranes (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). Human-to-human transmission is firmly established, with estimates indicating that, without control measures, each patient could infect two to three others (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). The range of individual COVID-19 health outcomes varied widely, from severe, life-threatening cases to completely asymptomatic individuals. The pandemic's effects extended far beyond the individual, causing widespread disruptions to global health and the world economy. The toll was immense, resulting in a significant loss of life and economic damages surpassing hundreds of billions of United States Dollars (Nicola et al., 2020).

By mid-July 2020, the pandemic had left a staggering toll in its wake: 14 million individuals were infected, 7.7 million were considered cured, and a loss of approximately 600,000 lives (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). Nevertheless, the extent of the afflicted and deceased remains uncertain owing to limited testing and potential underreporting (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). The COVID-19 global health crisis has also disproportionately impacted older adults and those with preexisting respiratory conditions or similar comorbidities (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021).

Despite the World Health Organization's (WHO's) efforts to mitigate the stigmatization of pandemic nomenclature, the year 2020 still witnessed significant biases driven by political affiliations (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021), namely in presidential speeches and social media content. Historically, epidemics and pandemics were given names indicating their place of origin, such as the "West Nile Virus," "Ebola Virus," and "Lhasa Fever" (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). In naming the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the WHO opted for a more diplomatically worded designation, aiming to protect the Chinese regions from stigma tied to the pandemic's beginnings (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). The WHO's approach involved naming the pandemic using the SARS-CoV-2 virus name

and emphasizing its molecular structure (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). This focus on the molecular level could be seen as a means to obscure the influence of economic and environmental factors in the emergence of new viral strains (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021).

COVID-19 Policies

The COVID-19 pandemic was met with several governmental policies and regulations to reduce infections and mitigate the spread and impact. Public health organizations such as WHO and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) advised individuals on everyday actions to protect themselves and others (Mahalik et al., 2021). These primary preventive measures included wearing masks covering the mouth and nose, regular hand washing, hand sanitizers, and maintaining physical distance (Shahrabani et al., 2022).

Most notably, the regulations were mask-wearing and social distancing or quarantine. A vast majority of countries implemented a set of preventive procedures and protocols that involved practices such as isolation, quarantine, community containment, and adhering to physical distancing, as well as conducting medical tests (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). Additionally, nations enforced travel restrictions, emphasized hand hygiene, and prohibited events and gatherings (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). The quarantine measures adopted by many countries sought to keep people confined to their homes, in prophylactic isolation, and, preferably, in a teleworking regime where the functions concerned were allowed (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). In some countries, individuals, including the sick and elderly, were to remain in their homes all day, although they could exercise once daily to buy food and other essential items (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). Several restrictions were imposed on the interactions between people who were not cohabiting; for example, they could not interact with more than one person at a time and should respect the distance of five feet from other people (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021).

Despite widespread international success in implementing social distancing and mask-wearing, which have helped other countries reach very low infection and mortality rates, the United States continued to experience high infection rates in various parts of the country. This was mainly due to the variability in Americans' adoption of the CDC's recommendations at both individual and community levels (Mahalik et al., 2021). At the peak of the first wave of the pandemic in April 2020, when most national governments imposed strict stay-at-home requirements, time spent at home increased by forty percent in some countries but just by around ten percent in others (Chen et al., 2021). These measures ultimately led to the temporary closure of several economic and social institutions, a relative national lockdown in several countries, and enormous pressure on health systems (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). Interestingly, countries such as Sweden, South Korea, and Taiwan did not impose total containment but followed a strategy that articulated quarantine targeting risk groups, monitoring, large-scale testing, and social distancing measures (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021).

Policymakers Involved

The sole policymakers responsible for decision-making during the COVID-19 pandemic were from the federal government. According to the CDC website, federal law grants authority for isolation and quarantine through the Commerce Clause of the U.S. Constitution. The law is stated as follows:

The federal government derives its authority for isolation and quarantine from the Commerce Clause of the U.S. Constitution. Under section 361 of the Public Health Service Act (42 U.S. Code § 264), the U.S. Secretary of Health and Human Services is authorized to take measures to prevent the entry and spread of communicable diseases from foreign countries into the United States and between states. The authority for

carrying out these functions daily has been delegated to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (Legal Authorities for Isolation and Quarantine | Quarantine | CDC, n.d.). Along with many members of Congress, the president of the United States is an integral part of decision-making regarding pandemic policies. Donald Trump was in office as the president of the United States during the 2019 and 2020 onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. According to The White House official government website, the “president is both the head of state and head of government of the United States of America and Commander-in-Chief of the armed forces. Under Article II of the Constitution, the President is responsible for the execution and enforcement of the laws created by Congress” (The White House, 2022). Donald Trump acted as the primary spokesperson throughout the pandemic, commenting on social media and speaking to the public over press conferences regarding pandemic procedures, policies, and regulations. His opinions were inconsistent with the key messages and did not match the efforts of public health experts, which will be explained further below.

The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) also played a crucial role in communicating with the United States during the COVID-19 pandemic. They are tasked with ensuring public health by guaranteeing the safety, effectiveness, and security of veterinary drugs, biological products, and medical devices, as well as overseeing the nation’s food supply, cosmetics, and radiation-emitting products (Food and Drug Administration (FDA) | USAGOV, n.d.). Their website states that the FDA is dedicated to offering timely guidance to support response efforts to the COVID-19 pandemic (Center for Devices and Radiological Health, 2023). During the COVID-19 pandemic, their key messages were to social distance, wear a face covering, and get vaccinated. Thus, this did not align with the president’s messages, which downplayed the severity of the virus and disease.

While not directly policymakers, experts play a pivotal role in influencing policymakers' opinions when creating and enforcing health policies. Among the experts during the COVID-19 pandemic were epidemiologists, virologists, and public health scientists (Antoci et al., 2022). Anthony Fauci, one such expert, holds the official title of director of the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases and is the chief medical advisor to the president of the United States. He essentially acted as the foremost health communication professional during the COVID-19 crisis. Fauci rose to popularity as he was consistently in the media advising the public on what to do. He consistently countered President Donald Trump's anti-scientific statements. Notably, he surged throughout the crisis, gaining traction not only among Democrats but even within some of the core demographics of Republicans (Antoci et al., 2022). His key messages were to follow regulations, and his demeanor was one of transparency and concern for the public. He provided commentary on the precautions the public should take and consistently emphasized the severity of the crisis. Some studies have shown that, overall, scientific experts are more trusted than political authorities (McClaughlin et al., 2023). This highlights the importance of ensuring that public guidance is grounded in scientific research (McClaughlin et al., 2023) and not just political ideologies.

The relationship between policymakers and experts is challenging, given their differing incentives, and the crisis had exacerbated existing disagreements (Cairney, 2021). In addition to this, some experts may align themselves with populist positions to gain visibility (Antoci et al., 2022), which negatively affects the public's trust in experts. This dynamic can potentially impede proper messaging and transparency when it comes to public health concerns. In February 2020, early warnings from doctors and scientists regarding the potentially disruptive effects of an escalating pandemic were met with skepticism by most political leaders, notably by President

Donald Trump, in the United States, despite the already observed impact in China (Antoci et al., 2022). Varying communicated messages during the pandemic are explained below.

Messages Communicated by the Policymakers

In 2020, the majority of messages from policymakers were delivered by then-President Donald Trump. Alongside these, there were messages from experts and constituents. People sought information from various sources. Many people were getting their sources of information from varying places.

Research by Antoci et al. (2022) highlights differing levels of public trust in both scientists and political leaders, especially during public health crises. This decline in trust was attributed to the emergence of science-related populism, as discussed by Mede and Schäfer (2020). This shift led to specific segments of the public losing confidence in scientists and academic institutions. As a result, some individuals began to favor political leaders who questioned the role of science in public discourse, exemplified prominently by Donald Trump during his presidency from 2017 to 2021.

In the early stages of the COVID-19 outbreak in China, the Trump Administration responded by downplaying the threat, exhibiting inaction, and implementing only partial measures. This led to confusion and the dissemination of inaccurate information (Parker & Stern, 2022). Consequently, opportunities to curb the spread through a robust public health response, including measures like testing, contact tracing, and isolation, were missed after the first case was confirmed in the United States on January 21, 2020 (Parker & Stern, 2022).

Appendix A demonstrates that Donald Trump used racial language when referring to the SARS-CoV-2 virus, dubbing it the "China Virus," as he repeatedly assured U.S. citizens that there was no need for concern or precautions.

In the case of COVID-19, policymakers initially implemented a cautious, phased communication strategy for social distancing, aiming to flatten the curve while maintaining political unity and economic activity. However, as the outbreak escalated beyond control, governments pragmatically transitioned from this approach to imposing strict stay-at-home orders (Amuedo-Dorantes et al., 2021). Government officials explained and defended their restrictive measures, with the help of the press, by stressing the deadly potential of COVID-19, with TV channels perpetuating footage of overcrowded emergency rooms, dead bodies, and piled-up coffins (Reed, 2020). These could otherwise be known as fear appeals.

Fear appeals, as defined by Berry (2006) and cited in McClaughlin et al. (2023), are persuasive messages that underscore the adverse physical or social consequences of not adhering to the recommendations in the message. McClaughlin et al. (2023) assert that effective fear appeals highlight the seriousness of the threat, substantiate the audience's susceptibility, and propose straightforward actions to mitigate the threat. The efficacy of these appeals is influenced by the perceptions of the advantages of taking action, as well as internal factors such as symptoms and external factors like mass media campaigns (McClaughlin et al., 2023).

The Health Belief Model uses perceived benefits to explain why people take action. Although perceived benefits are one persuasive strategy in getting individuals to change their health behavior, fear tactics can be used as well, as shown in the COVID-19 pandemic media responses. During the COVID-19 pandemic, public health campaigns were crafted to raise the salience of death, which researchers have argued may have led to an increase in people's death anxiety (Menziez and Menziez, 2020). The notion underlying these campaigns was that, by heightening the salience of personal vulnerability and death, fear of COVID-19 would increase,

and people would be more likely to comply with and accept the severe and unprecedented restrictions (Kehr et al., 2022).

Kehr et al. (2022) also proposed that individuals who experience death anxiety are more likely to exhibit fear of COVID-19, leading to increased adherence to government-imposed regulations. This hypothesis finds support in further research, which demonstrates a positive correlation between fear of COVID-19 and compliance with government-mandated measures (Kehr et al., 2022). Harper et al. (2021) observed a significant association between fear of COVID-19 and heightened behavioral compliance with personal restrictions mandated by the government. Furthermore, Zettler et al., in line with Kehr et al. (2022), reported that elevated levels of anxiety and fear were linked to greater acceptance of COVID-19-related measures. These fear tactics were used throughout the COVID-19 pandemic to try to get the public to comply and ultimately to help the population and mitigate the effects of the virus and disease.

Messages from Policymakers to Stakeholders

During the COVID-19 pandemic, policymakers communicated important directives to stakeholders. These included mandates for mask-wearing and practicing social distancing. Stakeholders, who will be discussed in more detail below, generally followed these guidelines to the best of their abilities. Health and risk communication research offers valuable insights for effective public health messaging from policymakers to stakeholders. One critical aspect highlighted is the need for consistency in messaging, as emphasized by Seeger (2006). However, maintaining this consistency proved challenging during the dynamic COVID-19 pandemic (McCloughlin et al., 2023). This was due to the varying approaches adopted by cities and states in their communication about mask-wearing and vaccine mandates.

Stakeholders Involved

Stakeholders are individuals or entities with a vested interest in the success of an organization or individual. They represent groups whose interests may be impacted by decision outcomes and possess the ability to influence these decisions, either directly or indirectly. The prosperity of an organization is of paramount importance to its stakeholders, as it plays a crucial role in achieving their objectives and significantly contributes to their overall progress.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the stakeholder group encompassed a wide range of entities, including governmental authorities like the World Health Organization and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. The WHO was a pivotal stakeholder during the COVID-19 pandemic. Their key stakeholders were Ministries of Health, government agencies, and other government departments at the national level (Stakeholders, n.d.). WHO also worked with influencers, including health partnerships, foundations, intragovernmental and nongovernmental organizations, civil society, media, professional associations, and WHO collaborating centers (Stakeholders, n.d.).

The various other stakeholders included healthcare providers such as primary care doctors, emergency room doctors and nurses, dentists including Heartland Dental, chiropractors, clinical psychologists, surgeons, and clinical social workers. It also extended to employers, spanning businesses of all sizes, including Fortune 500 companies like Walmart. In addition, pharmacies like Walgreens and CVS, insurance companies like Humana, Blue Cross Blue Shield, and Anthem, as well as scientists including virologists, pharmaceutical companies including Pfizer and Madera, and Johnson & Johnson, non-governmental organizations including the Red Cross, and educational institutions all constitute integral parts of the stakeholder collective.

These stakeholders have all been affected by the pandemic in different ways, and they have all played a role in the response to the pandemic. Healthcare providers had to adapt to the challenges of treating the COVID-19 virus, including implementing measures to ensure their own safety in the face of its high contagion rate. Employers had to make difficult decisions about how to keep their businesses running while protecting their employees. Pharmacies had to increase their supplies of medications and medical devices, while insurance companies had to cover the costs of medical care for many new patients. Additionally, corporations held a pivotal stake in the COVID-19 pandemic, with their interests encompassing consumers, employees, business partners, and governments (Bae et al., 2021).

Messages Communicated by Stakeholders

During the COVID-19 pandemic, various stakeholders, including those in the private sector and healthcare providers, actively communicated crucial messages. Organizational involvement was paramount in crafting effective COVID-19 communications, aligning with social responsibility commitments (Jiang & Dodoo, 2021). This effort served to educate the public on protective measures and governmental initiatives to curb the spread of COVID-19. Notably, certain organizational and brand signage employed gain-framed messages, emphasizing the positive outcomes of wearing face masks rather than relying on fear-based appeals (Jiang & Dodoo, 2021). Gain-framed messages focus on attaining the desirable outcome and avoiding the undesirable outcome (Toll et al., 2007). These signs cater to the diverse interests of individuals while also advocating for the importance of mask-wearing (Jiang & Dodoo, 2021). Most organizational stakeholders adhered to COVID-19 policies.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, social media, particularly Twitter, played a significant role in disseminating health information (Stevens & Palomares, 2022). Public health agencies

utilized Twitter to amplify this information (Stevens & Palomares, 2022). Mayo Clinic, a renowned hospital, demonstrated exemplary communication during the pandemic, as evidenced in Appendix B and C. They effectively used Twitter and a dedicated newsroom to emphasize crucial messages on self-protection, including the importance of mask-wearing and vaccination. Additionally, they employed social media and meme strategies to counteract false information, as shown in Appendix D. This approach aligned with governmental policies. They also provided support through a dedicated "COVID Recovery and Support Group" on their website, and as shown in Appendix C, which underscored their commitment to working alongside policymakers.

In addition to medical healthcare providers, dentists also communicated messages during the crisis. For example, Heartland Dental, a major dentistry chain in the United States, similarly aligned itself with policymakers during this period. Appendix E and F demonstrate their efforts on Facebook and Twitter, urging clients to wear masks in public settings.

Among the stakeholders involved were the influential Fortune 500 corporations. Walmart, a leading retailer in the United States, initially maintained a relatively quiet stance at the onset of the pandemic. It was after the CDC's recommendation regarding indoor face coverings that they actively engaged with their customer base. In 2020, via Twitter, as shown in Appendix G, they communicated their adherence to CDC guidelines, emphasizing the role of face coverings in reducing COVID-19 transmission for the safety of their customers and informing customers about the new requirement for face coverings in stores. In Appendix H, diverse reactions were observed. Some expressed feeling safer with this mandate, while others expressed frustration about the new requirement. In response, Walmart's social media manager promptly addressed customer concerns regarding the mandatory mask policy. As with a good

communication strategy, they encouraged customers to continue the conversation through private messages on Walmart's Facebook page, redirecting them from public comments on posts.

Constituents

Constituents are individuals within a defined geographical area who participate in the election process to choose a representative for a legislative body. They constitute the essential members comprising the entirety of this group. These individuals collectively form the electorate that exercises their voting rights to select a representative to advocate for their interests and concerns in the legislative arena.

Messages Among the Constituents

Amid the widespread global COVID-19 pandemic, social media had exacerbated the spread of health misinformation and disinformation. Belief in false health information was just as common as endorsing accurate information (Stevens & Palomares, 2022). The politicized and polarized state of information surrounding COVID-19 in the United States fueled an “infodemic” on social media, where facts were subjective depending on one’s political agenda (Stevens & Palomares, 2022). Because of this, many people during the crisis were part of echo chambers online. This is where constituents exclusively receive information from sources they follow or are already connected with. This can result in a lack of critical engagement and a failure to challenge pre-existing opinions.

Public health agencies frequently utilized Twitter as a means to disseminate and amplify the spread of COVID-19 information to constituents, which resulted in two-way conversations among themselves. Public health agencies shared valid information and details of their concerted efforts to protect constituents, but politicians were equally likely to sometimes distribute misinformation via tweets to pursue political agendas that could harm their constituents (Stevens

& Palomares, 2022). In fact, incongruencies in tweets existed in COVID-19 messaging across unique state public health agencies and individual stakeholders' Twitter accounts (Stevens & Palomares, 2022).

Stevens & Palomares (2022) found that while overall endorsement of COVID-19 misinformation is consistent across political parties, there's a nuanced difference in how Republicans and Democrats interpret government efforts. Republicans' positive views of local government actions can amplify belief in misinformation due to their reliance on politics over science in pandemic communication. This highlights a politically driven aspect of constituent communication. This split in political parties and differences in opinions caused constituents to disagree and argue with one another over COVID-19 policies.

Messages from Constituents to Stakeholders and Policymakers

Constituents received their COVID-19 regulation and policy information from varying channels and sources. According to Al-Metwali et al. (2021), 68.3% of participants obtained COVID-19 vaccine information from social media, newspapers, and television. In contrast, 44.7% relied on scientific sources like webinars or publications, while 20.1% turned to healthcare providers (HCPs) such as physicians or pharmacists. Only 5.5% reported being misinformed (Al-Metwali et al., 2021). This means that a majority of constituents received their messages from stakeholders and policymakers via a mass communication means.

In the study by Al-Metwali et al. (2021) constituents gave opinions, with most being in consensus. They proposed a multi-pronged awareness campaign and emphasized the importance of mandatory vaccination. They also advocated for healthcare workers' guidance and awareness initiatives. Furthermore, participants recommended partnering with organizations like the WHO for effective awareness campaigns. (Al-Metwali et al., 2021). In the study conducted by Al-

Metwali et al. (2021), respondents suggested emphasizing utilizing media sources like social media and television to garner attention and enhance public trust. Numerous components were suggested by constituents for the campaigns, including providing detailed explanations of the vaccines, along with information about their benefits, complications, and adverse drug reactions, as well as dispelling vaccine misconceptions (Al-Metwali et al., 2021). These four components can be applied to the Health Belief Model, where complications and adverse drug reactions are perceived as barriers. Additionally, many respondents recommended ensuring the availability of vaccines and giving priority to healthcare workers and other frontline workers for vaccination (Al-Metwali et al., 2021).

In the study conducted by Al-Metwali et al. (2021), along with recommended and suggested communication and awareness campaigns, most constituents used social media to express their opinions on regulations. The messages varied greatly between Democrats and Republicans. Appendix J shows an example of the messages constituents sent via social media to the Trump administration during the pandemic.

Civic Engagement and the Consideration of the Position of Constituents

Transparent information presentation and involving constituents in decision-making processes are key factors in building trust in government and organizations (Hyland-Wood et al., 2021). In a public health crisis, transparency means revealing the evidence that informed recommendations, disclosing consulted parties, and outlining considered scenarios and trade-offs (Hyland-Wood et al., 2021).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, communication faced challenges. Regulations and policies were often implemented rapidly without significant input from constituents. It's important to acknowledge that civic engagement can be difficult in crisis situations, where swift,

life-saving decisions may necessitate imposing strict measures without extensive community involvement (Hyland-Wood et al., 2021). But, in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, the most effective approach to recovery would have involved active and continuous public participation and engagement with various stakeholders such as communities, industries, and organizations. This ensures that concerns and aspirations are acknowledged and considered (Covello, 2003).

Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, Anthony Fauci and his team emerged as prominent health communication figures, delivering crucial public messages. However, due to the stringent mandates enforced by the federal government, the general public had limited opportunities to express concerns or provide feedback through surveys or other channels.

Policy Outcome

Even though preventative measures were communicated to the public, there was still a plethora of deaths from the COVID-19 pandemic. Preliminary estimates suggest the total number of global deaths attributable to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 is at least 3 million, representing 1.2 million more deaths than officially reported (The True Death Toll of COVID-19: Estimating Global Excess Mortality, n.d.). Below, the paper will describe a study conducted by Dreher et al., published in the American Journal of the Medical Sciences in 2021 and sets out to explain the outcome of the impact of COVID-19 regulations and policies enacted.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, policies were implemented in different sequences and with varying levels of overlap. For instance, approximately half of the United States initiated school closures as their initial step in disease prevention, while others opted to begin with restrictions on large gatherings (Dreher et al., 2021). A few states put these policies into effect simultaneously, and none immediately moved to stay-at-home orders or business closures (Dreher et al., 2021). Overall, there was a spread in the timing of policies, with a slight grouping

of school closures and restrictions on large gatherings implemented earlier in the pandemic, followed by business closures and stay-at-home orders (Dreher et al., 2021). According to Kaplan-Meier analyses, implementing a stay-at-home order before reaching 500 cases was linked with a lower likelihood of reaching 1000 cases within five days.

While disease modeling has suggested that social distancing is a crucial measure for achieving certain goals, validating these findings with actual case data can enhance support from both policymakers and the public (Dreher et al., 2021). The research done by Dreher et al. (2021) suggests that stay-at-home orders, restrictions on large gatherings, closures of educational facilities, and non-essential businesses are all effective measures in reducing transmission rates and thereby "flattening the curve," with stay-at-home orders having the most significant impact.

According to Dreher et al. (2021), mandated non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) have been associated with reduced transmission, presumably due to reductions in community mobility, however, little has been done to characterize the impact of NPIs in states with poor compliance. Studies conducted by Dreher et al. (2021) stated there were no statistically significant differences between states with or without a stay-at-home order in population density, hospital beds per 1,000 people, physicians per 1,000 people, percent current smokers, percent with COPD, percent with diabetes, or percent with cardiovascular disease (Dreher et al., 2021).

In summary, preliminary estimates indicate that the global death toll due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which took place in 2020, is likely higher than officially reported, with at least 3 million deaths recorded. The study conducted by Dreher et al. (2021) examined the impact of various policies and regulations implemented during the pandemic. The timing and sequence of these measures varied across states, with school closures and restrictions on large gatherings often being among the earliest implemented. Implementing stay-at-home orders before a certain

case threshold was associated with a lower likelihood of rapid COVID-19 case escalation. However, the study found that none of the examined policies, including stay-at-home orders, were linked to a decrease in the case fatality rate. Adherence to social distancing also varied between states despite similar policy implementations. The research suggests that measures such as stay-at-home orders, restrictions on large gatherings, closures of educational facilities, and non-essential businesses can effectively reduce transmission rates and "flatten the curve," with stay-at-home orders having the most significant impact. Additionally, mandated non-pharmaceutical interventions have been associated with reduced transmission, particularly due to subsequent reductions in community mobility.

The study also highlights that compliance with these measures played a crucial role in their effectiveness. Additionally, there were no statistically significant differences in various demographic and healthcare-related factors between states with or without a stay-at-home order. This underscores the importance of considering compliance and behavioral aspects when implementing public health measures.

COVID-19 Pandemic and Compliance

One of the most difficult challenges for policymakers during the COVID-19 pandemic was to get the general public to comply. For policies to be effective, a significant portion of the population must follow them. Several personal factors affected whether individuals complied with governmental COVID-19 regulations and policies. Shahrabani et al., (2022) explain that two distinct groups differ in their characteristics and influences of COVID-19 regulation adoption. Group A, referred to as the Eudaimonic group, consisted of individuals who demonstrated high levels of adherence to public health guidelines, possessed a greater trust in the government, felt more threatened by the pandemic, and tended to be older and female

(Shahrabani et al., 2022). On the other hand, Group B, known as the Hedonic group, comprised individuals displaying lower compliance with public health guidelines, leaned towards political conservatism, subscribed to conspiracy theories, and perceived less threat from the pandemic (Shahrabani et al., 2022).

In the following sections, the paper will focus on various personal facets of compliance during the COVID-19 pandemic, including political affiliation, gender differences, levels of trust in the government, and social norms.

Compliance and Political Affiliation

One of the complicating factors in gaining control over the COVID-19 virus in the U.S. was the politicization of efforts to combat it (Mahalik et al., 2021). In a survey conducted in mid-March 2020, Kushner Gadarian et al. (2020) reported that political affiliation was the strongest predictor of whether people followed public health recommendations, with Democrats more inclined than Republicans to engage in practices like handwashing, purchasing hand sanitizer, and maintaining social distancing. Democrats were also more likely to have adhered to social distancing recommendations (Kaiser Family Foundation, 2020). Whereas conservative rhetoric connected to Republican politicians is associated with more misinformation, democratic rhetoric is more consistent with guidelines from public health officials (Stevens & Palomares, 2022). As a result, United States partisan affiliation is a stronger predictor of COVID-19 beliefs than local infection rates or demographics (Stevens & Palomares, 2022).

Compliance and Gender Differences

Not only were political affiliations predictors of whether people followed public health recommendations, but gender-based predictors were also present. According to Winter (2010), there was consistent evidence that more traditionally masculine men tended to endorse more

conservative political ideologies. It is predicted that ideology moderated the relationship between masculinity and the mediators adhering to COVID-19 policies in predicting men's attitudes toward mask-wearing (Mahalik et al., 2021). Winter (2010) stated that politically conservative men, who are more conforming to traditional masculine norms, reported experiencing fewer benefits from the recommendations, encountering more barriers to enacting them, having less confidence in scientific experts, and showing less empathy for individuals vulnerable to the COVID-19 virus. One explanation offered by recent research supports the role played by traditional masculine norms in not wearing masks, stating that men are more likely to experience stigma from wearing a mask because it is perceived as a sign of weakness (Capraro and Barcelo, 2020)

Trust in the Government

The ability to garner population cooperation and maintain the behaviors required for controlling pandemics depends on endorsing trust (Alsaqqa, 2021). Trust in government represents the confidence or satisfaction of people with government performance and the perceived credibility of government. Recent studies conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic confirm that public trust in the government is crucial for encouraging the implementation of social policies that rely on behavioral adherence among the public (Shahrabani et al., 2022). Trust in the authorities, particularly in the Ministry of Health in each country, is another factor that may be influential in making decisions about preventive behavior (Shahrabani et al., 2022). The uncertainties and partial mistrust of medical knowledge and information, along with the dissemination of conspiracy theories, have further contributed to the emergence of a pervasive sense of vulnerability that does not promote mental well-being (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). As stated by Schaivo (2014) the Biopsychosocial Model explains that poor health is not only a

physical phenomenon but also it is influenced by people's feelings, thoughts about health, and their quality of mental health.

In the context of COVID-19, low trust in government has been identified as a determining factor for the low usage of contact-tracing apps, alongside a lack of trust in the companies that developed the apps and the fear of being tracked (McClaughlin et al., 2023). Public mistrust may stem from historical issues and perceived institutional racism (Quinn, 2008).

Compliance and Social Norms

The potential for norms to influence individuals' behavior has long been recognized in psychology research (Lalot & Abrams, 2023). People are more likely to adopt a behavior if they perceive it as socially acceptable by a relevant group and already adopted by others (Cialdini, 2012). Unsurprisingly, during the COVID-19 pandemic, evidence confirms that individuals were more likely to adopt health-protective behavior and respect social distancing regulations if they perceived other people as doing the same (Peterson et al., 2021). People might adopt others' behaviors and opinions either because they want to be accepted in the group or because they use them as cues to the correct demeanor (Lalot & Abrams, 2023).

People's behavior is also affected by social expectations, such as how others are viewed, as well as moral norms and values (Alsaqqa, 2021). Social compliance inspired people to do what was right during the COVID-19 pandemic, allowing them to follow and internalize shared guidelines (Alsaqqa, 2021). According to one study conducted by Al-Metwali et al. (2021), 66.0% of their survey respondents reported willingness to vaccinate if their colleagues and friends were to be vaccinated first.

Application of Theories to COVID-19 Regulation and Policy Adoption

The application of the Health Belief Model and Knowledge Gap Theory demonstrates how communications regarding COVID-19 spread among the public, how the public reacted to those messages, which groups received and understood the information, and how quickly, if at all, the public adopted the COVID-19 regulations and policies. These theories also show several components and variables inherent in understanding and deciding to adopt a health behavior change. Below, the components of HBM are described and applied to the COVID-19 pandemic, primarily through a study conducted by Al-Metwali et al. (2021) along with other resources.

Health Belief Model

The Health Belief Model (HBM) is a widely used framework in health communication and behavior change research. HBM was developed initially in the 1950s by academic and social psychologists Irwin M. Rosenstock, Godfrey M. Hochbaum, S. Stephen Kegeles, and Howard Leventhal in the U.S. Public Health Service to explain the widespread failure of people to participate in programs to prevent and detect disease (Hochbaum, 1958). Later, the model was extended to study people's responses to symptoms (Kirscht, 1974) and their behaviors in response to a diagnosed illness, particularly adherence to medical regimens (Becker, 1974). Academic social psychologists were developing an approach to understanding behavior that grew from learning theories derived from two primary sources: Stimulus-Response (S-R) Theory (Watson, 1925) and Cognitive Theory (Lewin, 1951).

Health Belief Model and S-R Theorists

S-R theorists propose that learning results from reinforcements, events that reduce physiological drives triggering behavior (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). Skinner (1938) formulated the widely accepted idea that a behavior's frequency is determined by its

consequences or reinforcement (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). According to Skinner, a simple temporal association between a behavior and an immediate reward increases the likelihood of the behavior recurring (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). In this view, concepts like reasoning or thinking are unnecessary to explain behavior (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, there were significant changes in daily routines and behaviors for individuals worldwide. Implementing pandemic policies and regulations triggered various responses from people, as they started practicing behaviors like wearing masks, social distancing, and obtaining vaccines in response to the threat of the virus. In the context of S-R theorists, these behaviors were reinforced by reducing the physiological chance of contracting or spreading the virus. The fear and anxiety associated with COVID-19 were powerful drives that activated these behaviors. The immediate reward or reinforcement, in this case, was the perceived reduction in the risk of contracting or spreading the virus.

Health Belief Model and Cognitive Theorists

Cognitive theorists highlight the significance of individuals' subjective hypotheses and expectations in shaping behavior (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). They argue that behavior is influenced by how a person subjectively values a certain outcome and the likelihood they believe a specific action will lead to that outcome (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). These perspectives are commonly referred to as value-expectancy theories. Thinking, reasoning, hypothesizing, and expecting are considered fundamental elements in all cognitive theories.

Unlike behaviorists, cognitive theorists suggest that reinforcements indirectly affect behavior by influencing expectations about a situation (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). In the context of health-related behaviors, it is assumed that individuals place a high value on avoiding

illnesses and seeking wellness. They also expect that a specific health action can prevent illness (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). This expectancy is further defined in terms of an individual's estimations of their own susceptibility to and perceived severity of an illness, as well as the likelihood of being able to mitigate that threat through personal action (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008).

In the COVID-19 pandemic, cognitive theorists focused on individuals' beliefs and expectations. They say our actions depend on how much we value an outcome and how likely we think a specific action will lead to that outcome (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). This applies to COVID-19, where people might have beliefs about policies and regulations like wearing masks, social distancing, and getting vaccinated.

Cognitive theorists argue that thinking, reasoning, and forming hypotheses are crucial for how people comprehend information about COVID-19, assess risks, and make decisions. Factors such as public health campaigns and incentives for vaccination can shape expectations regarding these actions. Individuals consider it essential to avoid illness and believe that specific behaviors can contribute to that goal. They also evaluate the likelihood of becoming sick, the severity of the illness, and whether their actions can effect change.

Components of Health Belief Model and Application to the COVID-19 Pandemic

The Health Belief Model (HBM) encompasses several components that predict whether individuals will take action to prevent, screen for, or control illness conditions. These components include perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefits, perceived barriers, cues to action, and, most recently, self-efficacy (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). In addition to describing these components, the application of HBM in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic has been clarified below.

Perceived susceptibility

Perceived susceptibility refers to an individual's belief about the likelihood of acquiring a disease (Al-Metwali et al., 2021). HBM emphasizes the importance of an individual's perception of their susceptibility to a health threat and the severity of that threat. In the context of COVID-19, communication campaigns have focused on conveying the seriousness of the virus and the potential harm it can cause, particularly to vulnerable populations. The study conducted by Al-Metwali (2021) has shown that healthcare workers were significantly more accepting of vaccination than the general population. One possible explanation might be the perceived risk of contracting the infection through direct involvement with COVID-19 patients or due to a higher level of medical knowledge (Al-Metwali et al., 2021). The study conducted by Al-Metwali et al. (2021) showed that over 60% of participants expressed concerns about contracting the infection, believed they were susceptible to it, and were at high risk.

Perceived Severity

This component shows the severity of the outcome the individual believes will be if action is not taken. This includes assessments of medical and clinical outcomes, like death, disability, and pain, as well as potential social repercussions, such as impacts on employment, family dynamics, and social interactions (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). The results from the study conducted by Al-Metwali et al. (2021) showed that through perceived susceptibility, a high number of respondents reported being at high risk of infection. Through perceived severity, most people reported concerns about the infection, believed COVID-19 infection to be fatal, and perceived it to be more serious than influenza infection.

Perceived Benefits

Even if a person perceives personal susceptibility to a serious health condition, whether this perception leads to behavior change will be influenced by the person's beliefs regarding the perceived benefits of the various available actions for reducing the disease threat (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). In the case of COVID-19, communication efforts aimed to highlight the benefits of preventive measures like wearing masks, practicing social distancing, and getting vaccinated while addressing concerns and misconceptions. As far as perceived benefits, more than half of the respondents in the study perceived the vaccines as effective, thought of them as ways to protect themselves, and thought of vaccines as a way to protect their families from the infection (Al-Metwali et al., 2021). Likewise, a study conducted in the U.S. in 2021 found the perceived benefit of the vaccines and perceived susceptibility to infection to be significant predictors of vaccination acceptance (Al-Metwali et al., 2021).

Perceived Barriers

The potential negative aspects of a particular health action, perceived barriers, may stop individuals from adopting the recommended behaviors, regulations, and policies (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). A decision process happens when individuals weigh the action's expected benefits with perceived barriers (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008).

The barriers to COVID-19 vaccination acceptance primarily involve concerns about storage conditions and adverse events following vaccination, with less than half addressing the vaccine's effectiveness (Al-Metwali et al., 2021). The qualitative data collected also revealed barriers contributing to participants' hesitation to receive the vaccines. Common barriers mentioned included worries about storage conditions, a preference for alternative infection prevention methods such as wearing masks or relying on natural immunity, the absence of long-

term studies, and concerns regarding the vaccines' effectiveness and adverse events (Al-Metwali et al., 2021). Cues to Action

Various early formulations of the HBM included the concept of cues that can trigger actions (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). Hochbaum (1958), for example, thought that readiness to act, perceived susceptibility, and perceived benefits could only be potentiated by other factors, particularly by cues to action, such as bodily events, or by environmental events, such as media publicity. A cue can be as fleeting as a sneeze or the barely conscious perception of a poster (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008). HBM emphasizes the role of cues to action. Communication strategies have used various cues, such as public health messages, news reports, and social influence, to motivate individuals to adopt preventive behaviors. According to the study conducted by Al-Metwali et al. (2021), the cues to actions domain indicated openness to vaccine recommendations from three main entities: the World Health Organization (WHO), healthcare providers, and the media.

Self-Efficacy

This term is defined as “the conviction that one can successfully execute the behavior required to produce the outcomes” (Bandura, 1997). In the study, Bandura (1997) differentiated self-efficacy expectations from outcome expectations, which are defined as a person’s estimate that a specific behavior will lead to certain outcomes. These outcomes may include demographic, psychological, and structural factors (Al-Metwali et al., 2021). The Health Belief Model (HBM) acknowledges that individuals must believe in their ability to perform a recommended behavior. Self-efficacy communication efforts have concentrated on building confidence in people's ability to adhere to COVID-19 regulations and providing clear instructions and resources for implementation (Champion & Sugg Skinner, 2008).

Self-efficacy messaging provides specific harm-reducing instructions for people affected by underlying health conditions, for people interacting with those at risk, or, in the case of COVID-19, for the general public (McClaughlin et al., 2023). In providing specific information on reducing harm, self-efficacy messages offer a sense of control over the risk factors (Seeger, 2006, p. 242). As long as the reason for a suggested action is clear, the recommended action is meaningful, and the action has real and apparent utility in reducing the harm (Seeger, 2006), self-efficacy messages can inspire the public's confidence that it is possible to collectively achieve a positive health outcome by adhering to the guidance they contain. Focusing exclusively on personal responsibility can be counter-productive, however, and has been associated with a higher risk of non-compliance (Institute of Medicine, 2015).

HBM: Influence and Efficacy of Communications During the COVID-19 Pandemic

The Health Belief Model shows that many individuals did not adopt behaviors that would protect themselves from contracting the COVID-19 virus. Kehr et al. (2022) stated that in a Swiss sample of young adults, the authors found that individuals living with a member of a risk group had higher compliance with, but not higher acceptance of, COVID-19 measures. The authors also reported that individuals' perceptions of the social risk of the coronavirus led to increased acceptance of the COVID-19 measures, but their perceptions of personal risk did not (Kehr et al., 2022). Therefore, fear of COVID-19 is associated with increased compliance with and acceptance of government-imposed COVID-19 restrictions (Zettler et al., 2020).

Supported by substantial research literature by Carpenter (2010), the Health Belief Model can be used to show that people are more likely to adopt recommended health practices if they believe they would produce benefits that outweigh their perceived barriers. For example, the perceived benefits would be to keep their loved ones healthy and to end the pandemic, and the

perceived barriers would include inconvenience and how wearing masks makes one look weak or afraid (Mahalik et al., 2021). Regarding gender, research examining men's health beliefs finds conformity to masculine norms to be associated with perceiving fewer benefits to healthy behaviors (Mahalik and Burns, 2011). As such, health beliefs about the benefits of, and barriers to, following CDC recommendations should relate to men's health practices and attitudes toward mask-wearing, such that higher levels of conformity to masculine norms may be associated with being less likely to view mask-wearing as beneficial as well as perceiving more barriers to wearing masks, for example, the fear of stigma or being perceived as weak (Mahalik et al., 2021). Similarly, one's trust and confidence in scientific experts and the perceived value of science-informed health policy have also been reported to relate to whether persons follow scientific recommendations concerning the COVID-19 pandemic (Plohl and Musil, 2020).

HBM is a valuable framework for understanding people's attitudes toward vaccination. It helps explore why some individuals are open to vaccinating while others may be hesitant or unwilling (Al-Metwali et al., 2021).

In the study conducted by Al-Metwali and colleagues (2021), several factors were identified that associate with the willingness to receive the COVID-19 vaccine. These include beliefs in preventive measures, recognition of the benefits of vaccination, consideration of potential barriers, external cues prompting action, social influence, general support for vaccination, and past flu vaccine history. However, the analysis also revealed that identifying as male and perceiving significant barriers were linked to a lower willingness to vaccinate against COVID-19 (Al-Metwali et al., 2021).

In Al-Metwali's (2021) study, the majority (68.3%) of participants turned to different media sources, such as social media, newspapers, and television, for information on the potential

COVID-19 vaccine. Throughout the pandemic, social media, being easily accessible and cost-effective, played a critical role in disseminating information.

However, it is important to acknowledge that media can have both positive and negative effects. While it effectively shares information, it can also contribute to the rapid spread of misinformation, potentially nurturing negative attitudes toward vaccines. Participants voiced concerns about various aspects of the vaccine, including its effectiveness, potential side effects, storage conditions, limited evidence from clinical trials, and prevalent misconceptions.

Concerning the HBM domains, most respondents highlighted their perceived susceptibility and severity regarding COVID-19 and the perceived benefits of the vaccine. (Al-Metwali et al., 2021).

In terms of HBM, the comments from the awareness campaign primarily focused on enhancing the perceived benefits of the vaccine and increasing the perceived severity of COVID-19. Additionally, they referred to cue-to-action strategies from the MOH, the WHO, and media awareness campaigns (Al-Metwali et al., 2021).

Policymaker and Stakeholder Communication with HBM

The Health Belief Model has proven to be a valuable framework for understanding and influencing individual behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic. By utilizing its components, communication strategies have been better tailored to encourage the adoption of recommended preventive measures and vaccination. In the study by Al-Metwali et al. (2021), participants viewed the World Health Organization (WHO) and healthcare providers as trustworthy sources of recommendations. They also emphasized the need for comprehensive awareness campaigns with diverse strategies to increase vaccination acceptance. This suggests that communication

from policymakers and stakeholders should align with the sentiments expressed by constituents in the study and prioritize awareness messages.

Participants further indicated that an effective campaign should highlight the benefits of vaccination, dispel misconceptions, and underline the severity of the disease (Al-Metwali et al., 2021). Additionally, public health officials should address concerns about vaccine effectiveness, potential adverse events, and storage to reduce perceived barriers to vaccination (Al-Metwali et al., 2021).

HBM explains why some people do not engage in programs that could prevent or treat diseases. It highlights factors like how likely they think they are to get sick, how serious they believe the illness is, the benefits they expect from treatment, and the obstacles they perceive. In a podcast on NPR Wisconsin Public Radio, Simmons-Duffin (2022) discusses the hurdles in accessing and using COVID-19 tools. These obstacles included expensive prescription drugs and the complex healthcare system, which are also issues faced with HIV-related tools like medications, gels, and injections that could benefit HIV-positive individuals but are not reaching them (Simmons-Duffin, 2022).

Perceived barriers act as a deterrent for people to join health programs. For COVID-19, some, particularly younger individuals, may not see themselves as likely to catch the virus or view it as a serious threat. This lack of understanding about the virus's risk and severity hinders people from getting vaccinated. This not only puts them at risk but also contributes to the susceptibility of the entire community, particularly vulnerable groups like those in retirement homes, facilities for people with disabilities, or incarcerated individuals (Simmons-Duffin, 2022).

Knowledge Gap Theory

In 1970, three researchers, Tichenor, Donohue, and Olien, began researching whether broadcast media, particularly television, could enable people with lower literacy levels to absorb information more quickly, as it does not require advanced reading skills. However, their study revealed the presence of a knowledge gap. This gap exists between individuals of high socioeconomic status and those of low socioeconomic status. The results indicate that both groups get information from media sources, but the high socioeconomic group processes it significantly faster than the low socioeconomic group.

According to the “knowledge gap hypothesis,” when information about a topic enters a social system, segments of the population with higher resources are better able to acquire this information “so that the gap in knowledge between these segments tends to increase rather than decrease” (Tichenor, Donohue, & Olien, 1970, pp. 159–160).

Research on knowledge gaps has emphasized the significant role of media in influencing informational disparities (Gerosa et al., 2021). There is substantial evidence indicating that different forms of media can have varying impacts on knowledge gaps, either amplifying, sustaining, or reducing them (Gerosa et al., 2021). Across a broad spectrum of studies, it has been observed that television tends to uphold existing gaps, while print and digital media appear to widen knowledge disparities among groups with varying educational backgrounds (Lind & Boomgaarden, 2019). Furthermore, other studies have addressed knowledge gaps associated with using digital media (Bonfadelli, 2002), focusing on social media. These studies have shown an amplifying effect, particularly in the case of social media platforms (Yoo & Gil de Zúñiga, 2014). One contributing factor to this is the “digital divide,” where some populations have full access to online resources while others do not.

Components of Knowledge Gap Theory and Application to the COVID-19 Pandemic

According to the Knowledge Gap Theory, there are five reasons why knowledge gap inequalities continue to exist. These reasons are communication skills, amount of stored prior knowledge of pertinent topics, relevant social contact, retention of information, and the nature of the mass media information delivery subsystems (Tichenor et al., 1970). During the COVID-19 pandemic, communication strategies have been tailored to address different population segments, considering factors like age, education level, cultural background, and access to resources (Al-Metwali et al., 2021). With the rise of misinformation and digital technologies like social media, this was met with challenges.

Communication Skills

One crucial factor affecting knowledge gaps is an individual's understanding and retaining information. Education and social status are key players in this dynamic (Tichenor et al., 1980, p. 181). Communication skills are instrumental in creating and sustaining these disparities in knowledge. Grasping and comprehending information about the new virus can literally be a matter of life or death (Gerosa et al., 2021). However, there has been a simultaneous surge in misinformation about COVID-19, potentially hindering people from accessing accurate guidance (Jurkowitz & Mitchell, 2020).

The knowledge gap hypothesis posits that higher socioeconomic status, particularly education level, is associated with greater knowledge on specific subjects. This knowledge disparity tends to widen as the volume of information in a social system increases (Tichenor et al., 1970). There is substantial evidence indicating knowledge disparities based on educational attainment across various subjects, including health, non-health-related scientific matters, and social as well as political issues (e.g., political stances and city budgets; for comprehensive

reviews, refer to Lind & Boomgaarden, 2019). Furthermore, individuals with higher levels of education might be more adept at handling information overload and Internet excess (Gui & Büchi, 2021), which were prominent features during the COVID-19 lockdown period.

In line with extensive research on the knowledge gap hypothesis (see Lind & Boomgaarden, 2019), this study confirms that during the initial phase of the pandemic, there was an education-related knowledge gap regarding COVID-19 risks and precautions. Specifically, individuals with at least a bachelor's degree exhibited higher levels of knowledge compared to those with lower educational attainment.

Relevant Social Contact

People typically seek information from their social connections, often bypassing social media platforms for direct interactions (Gerosa et al., 2021). Those with well-informed friends and family who could sift through the deluge of information in the initial stages may have gained valuable insights. This advantage might have been more prevalent among individuals with higher educational backgrounds (Gerosa et al., 2021). For instance, having contacts in the medical field could have been particularly beneficial (Gerosa et al., 2021).

The Extent of Prior Knowledge

The extent of prior knowledge an individual possesses is a key factor in perpetuating knowledge disparities. This hinges on access to resources like books and classrooms, which serve as reservoirs of knowledge (Tichenor et al., 1970). Education further amplifies this effect, with well-educated individuals benefiting from a richer reservoir of prior knowledge to comprehend new concepts.

In a study conducted by Gharpure et al. (2020), 39% of respondents reported engaging in non-recommended high-risk practices with the intent of preventing SARS-CoV-2 transmission,

such as washing food products with bleach, applying household cleaning or disinfectant products to bare skin, and intentionally inhaling or ingesting these products. Respondents who engaged in high-risk practices more frequently reported an adverse health effect that they believed resulted from using cleaners or disinfectants than those who did not report engaging in these practices (Gharpure et al., 2020). According to Gharpure et al. (2020) public messaging should have emphasized evidence-based, safe practices such as hand hygiene and recommended cleaning and disinfection of high-touch surfaces to prevent transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in household settings. The largest gaps were found in knowledge about the safe preparation of cleaning and disinfectant solutions and about the storage of hand sanitizers out of the reach of children (Gharpure et al., 2020).

Selective Exposure, Acceptance, and Retention of Information

Arousal and salience influence the selective exposure, acceptance, and retention of information (Gaziano, 2008), meaning that acceptance and retention are tied to the perceived importance of the information. In homogenous communities with similar interests and values, interpersonal communication prevails over mass communication, potentially narrowing knowledge gaps as people encounter a broader range of information from peers on a personal level. In contrast, mass communication takes precedence in more diverse communities with varied interests and values, potentially widening knowledge gaps as people receive a narrower range of information from the media (Gaziano, 2008).

Despite the knowledge gaps and high-risk practices identified in the study conducted by Gharpure et al. (2020), most respondents believed that they knew how to clean and disinfect their homes safely, thus, prevention messages should have highlighted identified gaps in knowledge about safe and effective practices and provide targeted information using innovative

communication strategies, including social media, regarding safe cleaning and disinfection. These messages about cleaning and disinfection practices for COVID-19 prevention could be coordinated and disseminated through trusted sources of information such as national, state, and local public health agencies and medical providers (Gharpure et al., 2020).

An increase in the amount of information offered by media on a topic will mainly benefit the highest socioeconomic segments of the population, who tend to acquire this information more easily and faster than their disadvantaged counterparts (Tichenor et al., 1970).

Nature of Mass Media Information Delivery Systems

The way mass media delivers information contributes to knowledge gaps. Different media types have distinct effects on knowledge gaps based on education levels (Gerosa et al., 2021). Regarding conventional news sources, research indicates a significant contrast between the impact of television and other media (Gerosa et al., 2021). This contrast arises from the specific characteristics of traditional media, particularly in terms of audience segmentation. Major TV channels reach a broad, socially diverse audience with standardized content, while newspapers reflect a country's citizens' geographical, political, and social diversity (Gerosa et al., 2021).

While the rapid dissemination of information during the COVID-19 crisis may have widened knowledge gaps, with highly educated people possessing more crucial information than others (Tichenor et al., 1970), it may also be that public health efforts to reach all audiences avoided knowledge gaps (Gerosa et al., 2021).

Knowledge Gap Theory: Influence and Efficacy of Communications During COVID-19

The health crisis of the COVID-19 pandemic in the spring of 2020 created a serious communication challenge as countries tried to contain the global pandemic. Since the beginning

of COVID-19, government authorities and media tried to communicate what was known day by day about the symptoms, the precautionary measures to avoid contagion, and the guidelines to follow as part of lockdown policies (Gerosa et al., 2021). In the context of COVID-19 regulations, this theory implies that these groups may be more inclined to understand and adhere to the recommended behaviors and restrictions. However, tailored communication strategies are crucial for behavior change to be effective across all segments of society, especially those with lower levels of education or socioeconomic status. The manipulation of information, poor content quality, and difficulties in accessing communication and information technologies affect individuals with fewer resources and enhance illiteracy, making them more likely to ignore the health warnings developed by the governments (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021).

The Knowledge Gap Theory suggests that people with lower socioeconomic status did not have as quick access to or understanding of COVID-19 policies as populations with higher socioeconomic status. This could have impacted the rate of COVID-19 policy following, as people who were less informed about the virus may have been more likely to believe misinformation about it, such as that masks are not effective or that the virus is not a serious threat. People who did not believe in adhering to COVID-19 regulations, such as mask-wearing, may have been following channels that spread misinformation about the virus. This correlates to the Knowledge Gap Theory, as these people only get limited information about the virus from unreliable sources. One qualifying factor for information access is geographical location, such as lower socioeconomic populations living in rural areas without high-speed internet or underserved populations.

Another theory that could be applied to this situation (NPR story) is the Knowledge Gap Theory can also be applied to the NPR podcast that was narrated by Simmons-Duffin (2022). In

the podcast, they explain how some underserved populations were not getting adequate access to health information, not getting it as quickly, or even possibly not fully understanding the severity of the disease or benefits of the treatments because of a lack of education.

The Term Social Distancing

As COVID-19 has spread throughout the world, the term “social distancing” has been widely used to encourage the general population to physically distance themselves from others to reduce the spread of the virus (Wasserman et al., 2020). However, this term had unintended but detrimental effects, as it evoked negative feelings of being ignored, unwelcome, left alone with one's own fears, and even excluded from society (Wasserman et al., 2020). These feelings may have been stronger in people with mental illnesses and in socioeconomically disadvantaged groups, such as stigmatized minorities, migrants, and homeless persons. Many of them also have high risk for suicidal behaviors (Wasserman et al., 2020) on top of having less and slower access to information that could keep them healthy during the pandemic.

Policymaker and Stakeholder Communication with Knowledge Gap Theory

People's engagement with and response to public health information and messaging is heavily influenced by their cultural and social identity, age, gender, and access to resources (Hyland-Wood et al., 2021). These factors influence people's preferred modes of communication, who and what they perceive as a ‘trustworthy authority,’ and, importantly, their capacity to act and respond to information (Hyland-Wood et al., 2021). Knowledge Gap Theory explains the reasons for the continued gap in knowledge, including those listed above. Much of the communication spread to the populations was over social media, broadcast television, and radio. Policymakers seemed not to have much of a strategy for incorporating Knowledge Gap Theory into the equation. Anthony Fauci, the health communication professional of that time,

tried his best to communicate the policies, regulations, and procedures the public should take to prevent disease and virus transferring.

Success or Failure of the Communications

Societal factors must be taken into account when developing a public health communication strategy, which, to be genuinely effective in engaging maximum public support and participation, needs to be sensitive to the concerns and values of diverse publics and work with different modes of information sharing (Hyland-Wood et al., 2021). Social media provides opportunities for this effective communication (Hyland-Wood et al., 2021), although when factoring in the Digital Divide and Knowledge Gap Theory, some populations do not have access to the information that is stored online. In addition to that, much of social media is echo chambers where constituents see the information that confirms their bias by following only people with similar beliefs as their. Social media, though, enables vital messages to be disseminated quickly and efficiently and to be appropriately tailored to different audiences (Hyland-Wood et al., 2021) when strategized properly. It also allows communities to become actively involved in sharing and honing relevant messages (Hyland-Wood et al., 2021). However, as stated earlier, it is also a place where misinformation can wreak havoc.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, social media significantly hindered practical communication efforts by public health experts and scientists. This was primarily due to a polarized political climate, which left many Americans apprehensive about politicizing health precautions. Consequently, public trust eroded on both political and stakeholder fronts, including among public health experts. Democrats largely lost trust in President Donald Trump and his administration, leading them to disregard their messages. Conversely, Republicans mistrusted

scientists and public health experts due to conflicting messages from the administration. The year 2020 saw a surge in misinformation and conspiracy theories.

The decline of trust led to reduced public cooperation. Trust is a crucial factor in mobilizing public cooperation and sustaining necessary behaviors for pandemic management (Agley, 2020). According to Siegrist and Zinng (2014), effective crisis communication in a pandemic relies on high levels of trust based on shared values among stakeholders, as well as confidence in the predictability of future developments.. Furthermore, public trust can rapidly deteriorate and remain low when government leaders appear unwilling to adhere to the rules and guidelines expected of the general public (Fancourt et al., 2020). In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, President Donald Trump publicly disregarded and urged citizens also to dismiss the recommendations of public health officials to curb the rapid spread of the virus.

Hyland-Wood et al. (2021) explain ten recommendations for communication during a public health crisis. These are: Engage in clear communication, strive for maximum credibility, communicate with empathy, communicate with openness, frankness, and honesty, recognize that uncertainty is inevitable, account for levels of health literacy and numeracy, empower people to act, appeal to social norms, consider diverse community needs, and be proactive in combating misinformation. In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, communication was not very clear as there were opposing parties of experts and politicians disagreeing with each other openly to the public.

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the enduring impact of policy decisions (Alsaqqa, 2021). People now seem less inclined to accept the notion that problems are too complex or time-consuming to address (Alsaqqa, 2021). Many countries faced strained healthcare systems, partially closed economies, and a shortage of essential resources during the

pandemic (Alsaqqa, 2021). It's imperative to involve communities and social networks in decisions that affect them (Miranti and Evans, 2019). Engaging stakeholders also significantly enhances the effectiveness of containment measures and fosters public cooperation (Renn, 2008). On the contrary, the outdated deficit communication model, which views it as a one-way process of "educating an ignorant public," is still in use (Meyer, 2016). This approach overlooks the importance of local knowledge and experiences in shaping effective policies (Hyland-Wood et al., 2021). In some instances of COVID-19 regulation communication, it appeared that health communication professionals were still relying on this outdated one-way communication method of informing the public.

Conclusion

In the early 21st century, the World Health Organization advised nations to brace themselves for a severe pandemic, a likelihood acknowledged since 2003. They urged all countries to form national pandemic planning committees (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). This marked a shift in health policy, as it integrated a culture of readiness with the existing focus on disease prevention (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). Readiness encompasses various concepts, strategies, and actions, which can be systematically outlined across three key areas: monitoring and early detection of significant epidemics, swift responses, and the efficient sharing of data, knowledge, and technology; and enhancement of global epidemic response governance (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021). The confusion and uncertainty surrounding the COVID-19 pandemic could have been significantly reduced with a more robust set of communication strategies based on these theories.

The Health Belief Model also played a crucial role in shaping preparedness strategies. This model emphasizes the importance of individual perceptions and beliefs in influencing health-related behaviors. In the context of pandemic preparedness, it highlights how people's

perceptions of the severity and susceptibility to a potential outbreak and the perceived benefits of preventive measures can significantly impact their willingness to comply with public health recommendations.

By incorporating the principles of the Health Belief Model into communication strategies, authorities could have effectively conveyed the seriousness of the situation, increased awareness about preventive measures, and addressed concerns that may have contributed to confusion during the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic. This could have resulted in a more unified and informed public response.

Furthermore, the HBM also underscores the importance of cues to action, which are prompts or triggers that stimulate individuals to take action to protect their health. These cues can be in the form of media messages, advice from healthcare professionals, or witnessing the experiences of others. In the case of pandemic preparedness, a well-designed communication plan utilizing various channels and sources of information could have served as powerful conveyors of cues to action, mobilizing individuals and communities to adopt preventive measures and adhere to public health guidelines (Ferreira & Serpa, 2021).

Chen et al.'s (2021) research highlights a significant correlation between regions with a higher prevalence of individualistic cultural traits and lower adherence to stay-at-home measures mandated by their respective governments. This finding underscores the need for tailoring communication strategies to align with cultural nuances and values. Had the United States considered its own individualistic tendencies and potential compliance challenges, it might have been possible to fine-tune communication efforts for better effectiveness. Recognizing and respecting cultural differences in responses to messaging is a crucial aspect of ensuring public health initiatives are met with success.

The study by Chen et al. (2021) underscores the importance of cultural competence in public health communication. By understanding and accounting for the cultural context, authorities can develop messages that resonate more effectively with diverse populations, ultimately enhancing compliance and mitigating confusion during critical public health situations like the COVID-19 pandemic.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, public health authorities widely employed fear-based strategies to promote compliance with regulations and policies. These tactics aimed to emphasize the disease's severity and individuals' potential susceptibility to contracting it. This approach aligns with the Health Belief Model, a psychological framework used to understand and predict health-related behaviors. According to the Health Belief Model, individuals are more likely to engage in behavior change if they perceive a health threat as serious and themselves as vulnerable to it. In the context of COVID-19, instilling fear about the severity of the virus and the potential consequences of contracting it can effectively motivate people to take precautionary measures.

By presenting COVID-19 as a serious and potentially life-threatening condition, authorities sought to increase public awareness about the risks associated with the virus. This awareness, coupled with the belief that individuals are susceptible to infection, catalyzes behavior change. People were more inclined to adopt preventive measures such as wearing masks, practicing social distancing, and adhering to lockdowns and stay-at-home orders. Using fear tactics during the pandemic was not merely a sensationalist approach but a strategic application of psychological principles. By aligning messaging with the Health Belief Model, authorities aimed to influence public behavior to prioritize individual and collective health and safety.

In addition, the Knowledge Gap Theory shows that populations must be segmented. Communication strategies must be applied to groups based on their criteria of education level, communication skills, social contacts, how much knowledge they have about a health topic, how easily they can retain the information, and how the nature of the mass media information system can affect the way lower socioeconomic populations gain knowledge slower than higher socioeconomic populations.

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Appendices

Appendix A – Donald Trump Response to COVID-19

Donald J. Trump · [Follow](#)

Dec 29, 2020 ·

\$2000 for our great people, not \$600! They have suffered enough from the China Virus!!!

Rob McLain and 733K others 130K comments 37K shares

Like

Comment

Share

Appendix B – Mayo Clinic Response to COVID-19

Severe lung damage has been a serious outcome for [#COVID19](#) patients who are facing recovery from the disease. Dr. Shah talks about COVID-19 lung damage, the speculation there will be an increased need for [#LungTransplants](#). Learn more. mayocl.in/3ntQ4yv

COVID-19 lung damage could lead to a transplant

11:18 AM · 12/21/20 from Earth

Appendix C – Mayo Clinic Response to COVID-19

-

By Deb Balzer
July 30, 2021
Protect yourself, others by getting vaccinated for COVID-19
-

By Jennifer O'Hara
July 30, 2021
Mayo Clinic Q&A podcast: Managing asthma in children
-

By Jason Howland
July 29, 2021
Mayo Clinic Minute: Study shows masks can prevent COVID-19
-

By Joe Dangor
July 29, 2021
Study shows masks offer protection as COVID-19 infections tick up

Appendix D – Mayo Clinic Fact Check

 · [Follow](#)
Dec 12, 2020 ·

Here is today's COVID-19 vaccine myth buster:

 MYTH: COVID-19 vaccines were developed to contr... See more

MYTH	FACT
COVID-19 vaccines contain microchips developed to control people.	There is no vaccine microchip. The vaccine cannot track people or gather personal information.
✗	✓

 2.9K 858 comments 2.1K shares

 Share

 · [Follow](#)
Dec 11, 2020 ·

Here is today's COVID-19 vaccine myth buster:

 MYTH: I won't need to wear a mask after I get vacci... See more

MYTH	FACT
I won't need to wear a mask after I get vaccinated for COVID-19.	After being vaccinated, it is unknown whether you can still transmit the virus. Continued mask usage is recommended.
✗	✓

 2.2K 1.5K comments 3.9K shares

 Share

Appendix E – Heartland Dental Response to COVID-19

 Heartland Dental · Follow ⋮
Apr 24, 2020 · 🌐

As we strive to “flatten the curve” across the United States, let’s all continue to do our part in limiting the spread of [#COVID19](#). Did you know that up to 1.65 million dental ER visits could be diverted from hospitals annually?

Right now, all of us in the dental community – organizations, dentists and patients alike – can show our support to those on the front lines of this pandemic by keeping [#DentalER](#) cases out of hospitals. If you have a dental emergency, contact your local dental office.

 57 33 shares

Appendix F – Heartland Dental Response to COVID-19

Heartland Dental @HeartlandDental · 5/15/20 ...

Many dental practices are implementing additional safety measures to align with traditional CDC and OSHA requirements. Here's how a trip to a Heartland Dental supported office may change as states reopen. [#COVID19](#) [#HeartlandDental](#)

FOR EXAMPLE, WE MIGHT:

Be wearing additional personal protection equipment

Request that you wear a mask to your appointment

Ask to take yours and other patients' temperatures upon arrival

Ask you to wash your hands for thirty seconds

Request that you wait in the treatment room or your vehicle instead of the waiting room

Request that you call in payment after your appointment, for example via credit card

Appendix G – Walmart Response to COVID-19

Walmart · Follow

Jul 15, 2020 ·

To best serve our communities and protect the health and safety of our shoppers and associates, face coverings will be required in all stores beginning Monday, July 20. For more on our decision and policy, please see here: <https://bit.ly/2DHFTUN>

37.5K

47.6K comments 35.3K shares

Like

Comment

Share

Appendix H – Constituent Responses to Walmart

 · Follow
 Jul 15, 2020 ·

 Londie Grothjan
 Masks should be voluntary not mandatory. Those concerned for their health should look into the options they suggest for others— curbside pick- up and online ordering.

3y Like Reply 198

 Author
 Hello, Londie. We know there may be situations where it may not be possible for someone to wear a face covering. Our ambassadors will be trained on those exceptions to help reduce friction for the shopper and make the process as easy as possible for everyone.

3y Like Reply 5

View 8 replies...

View 157 more replies...

 Write a reply...

 Teresa Wright
 Walmart will be losing my weekly business since you won't accept cash. I'll have to pay a little more for my groceries but that's ok. Your associates were rude when I asked about why they would not let me pay with cash. I'm done with Walmart.

3y Like Reply 4

 Author
 Hello, Teresa. That's not what we like to hear about our associates. Can you please send us a PM about this at <http://walmart.us/2E0Za3F>? Thank you

 · Follow
 Jul 15, 2020 ·

 Rosie Nicole Ritter
 Where do I report a store not following this? Counted 10+ customers yesterday without masks on. I find it inconsiderate for people not to follow the rules and care about the health and safety of others.

3y Like Reply 4

 Author
 Hi, Rosie. Could you PM us with more info, so we can help?
www.facebook.com/msg/walmart

3y Like Reply

View 2 more replies...

 Write a reply...

 Anthony Vee
 No mask was required when I went there today. I wore a mask but I saw the liaison at the door allowing people through. I was told they were there to remind people to wear the masks. Isn't that what the 15 signs all over the building were for? What are the people at the door there for? A paycheck? They're not doing their job, I was also told that if I wanted the face covering enforced that I personally would have to call the police, THEN and only then would they enforce it. Nice.

3y Like Reply 1

 Author
 Hi, Anthony. Could you tell us more about your recent visit?
www.facebook.com/msg/walmart

3y Like Reply

Appendix I – Constituent Responses to Mayo Clinic

 Mayo Clinic · Follow
Dec 11, 2020 · 🌐

2y Like Reply 4 🍌

 Joni Bontrager replied · 2 replies

 Jenn Anthofer
So, we are currently masking because anyone could be an asymptomatic carrier. And the vaccine is going to create a bunch of asymptomatic carriers? Sounds "great".
2y Like Reply 15 🍌❤️

 Alli Alley replied · 1 reply

 Taylor Osorio
Your sheeple have literally been told all along after they receive the vaccine they'll be able to live freely. Get it together. People who can't think for themselves are counting on you and other officials to think for them.
2y Like Reply 17 🍌

 Nikki Lynn
It would be amazing if medical establishments would start pushing true health and wellness. You know, taking care of your body properly? Good thing many people are realizing this on their own and leaving your fraudulent sick care behind!
2y Like Reply 5 🍌❤️

 Deborah Ann
I'm confused then. What about all the other vaccines? That means the people who get them are asymptomatic carriers after getting them then right? 😊
2y Like Reply 6 🍌❤️

 Celine Michelle Diaz replied · 4 replies

 Mayo Clinic · Follow
Dec 11, 2020 · 🌐

 Michael Howell
Yet how can we trust a vaccine that has been rushed through the typical lengthy evaluation process? There's zero history that I've seen of any C-19 vaccine having a thorough testing process. It's extremely unfortunate we've had fellow Americans lose their lives to Covid. There's more to this entire process than many realize. It's beyond tragic. My heart breaks for dear friends who've lost loved ones to this virus.
2y Like Reply 36 🍌❤️

 Gwen Tucker replied · 12 replies

 Faye Beaton McNamar
You have to give it time. We are all aware that it's going to take TIME for all shots to be done. It's not going to be fixed until every one has their shots. For me, I will wear my mask for as long as it takes to protect you and myself.
2y Like Reply 57 🍌❤️

 Margaret Just replied · 5 replies

 Sherri Hamilton
Like the flu shot it may not be 100% effective so you may get a milder case which means you can give it to someone else. It will take awhile to get this thing under control so think of others as well as yourself.
2y Like Reply 2 🍌

Appendix J – Constituent Responses to Donald Trump

 · [Follow](#)
Dec 29, 2020 ·

 Joyce A. Metcalf
PUT OUR AMERICAN PEOPLE FIRST AND OUR COUNTRY FIRST, CONGRESS, SENATE, ALL THE OTHER COUNTRIES WILL HAVE TO FIGURE OUT SOMETHING ELSE . WE THE PEOPLE OF THE UNITED STATES COMES FIRST. !!!!!!!!
2y Like Reply 1.1K

 Diatra Lewis replied · 45 replies

 Kristen Stevenson
Honestly, I just want my freedoms back. Keep the money.
2y Like Reply 1.7K

 Bruni Droste replied · 197 replies

 · [Follow](#)
We don't care if it is \$600 or \$2,000 we are happy that you were defeated by the great Joe Biden and we will use the money to celebrate your departure from the white House come January 20th, because you were the worst president ever to occupy the white House.
2y Like Reply 10K

 Bula Richard replied · 20,625 replies

 Darlene Pack Owens
Let's get this straight, the politicians haven't missed a check and don't break a sweat working but don't want to give US citizens 2000 but rather 600 and send millions to other countries or revamp museums or a library 😂😂😂. Wake up Americans! We need to remove 90% of all sitting politicians and judges with people that have some common intelligence.
2y Like Reply 1.6K